

A hybrid model for the prediction of magnetostriction in grain-oriented electrical steel coils

Technical Report

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This paper presents a hybrid model for the prediction of magnetostriction in power transformers by leveraging the strengths of a data-driven approach and a physics-based model. Specifically, a non-linear physics-based model for magnetostriction as a function of the magnetic field is employed, the parameters of which are estimated as linear combinations of electrical coil measurements and coil dimensions. The model is validated in a practical scenario with coil data from two different suppliers, showing that the proposed approach captures the different magnetostrictive properties of the two suppliers and provides an estimation of magnetostriction in agreement with the measurement system in place. It is argued that the combination of a non-linear physics-based model with few parameters and a linear data-driven model to estimate these parameters is attractive both in terms of model accuracy and because it allows training the data-driven part with comparably small datasets.

1 Introduction

The noise level of anthropic areas is rising, industrial and housing development are posing new environmental problems [1]. Power Transformers (PT) are a known source of noise and in recent times the European Parliament took action [6] to control and regulate noise pollution. This creates an incentive for companies to investigate ways to control the noise emissions of their PT. The magnetostrictive effect refers to the contracting and

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dilating of steel sheets in the magnetized core of a PT and is the main source of transformer core noise with a peak frequency at twice the input electromagnetic frequency [3, 7, 18], especially when the flux density exceeds 1.5 T [12]. As a characterization of magnetostriction, motivated by noise analyses, the $B8$ value, defined as the flux density at a magnetic field of 800 A/m, has been proposed [4]. However, the $B8$ value cannot completely characterize the no-load noise behavior of the PT. This was shown through measurements taken by the Coil Measurement System (CMS) described in [16]. This CMS is able to perform measurements on complete steel coils with a weight of up to 6,000 kg [16] and is used to study magnetostrictive properties of steel coils. Parameters known to influence the no-load noise of grain-oriented electrical steel (GOES) coils are cutting of the core material, mechanical stress, and coil dimensions (see [16, Section II.C] and the references therein). Due to all these factors and instabilities in the production process, coils with identical design may show different magnetostrictive properties [17].

This work proposes to model the effective vibration velocity, a proxy for magnetostrictive strain, as a function of coil dimensions, coil temperature, and coil measurements such as magnetic field, flux density, apparent power, and power factor. The model uses a data-driven approach to estimate the parameters of a physics-based model between magnetic field and magnetostrictive strain (cf. [8]). Specifically, this hybrid model captures non-linear dependencies in the physical model and uses linear regression to estimate the parameters of the model from other measurements. A separate set of experiments, not included in the paper, shows that replacing linear regression with more sophisticated non-linear methods does not increase the performance of the hybrid model, i.e., linear regression is selected. This makes the presented approach particularly suited for applications with small datasets, which prevent training of non-linear data-driven models.

The contribution of the paper is two-fold and benefits two fields of research. First, in the field of transformer coil measurements, the hybrid model can run in parallel to the measurement system as a means to verify the validity of the obtained measurements. It is thus a first step towards replacing difficult vibration measurements by predictions based on electrical measurements, which are usually much easier to obtain. Second, in the field of data science, the paper is a case study in hybrid modeling. It is shown that estimating the parameters of a non-linear physics-based model by a linear data-driven model leads to a greater accuracy than what would be achieved by using the physical model with averaged parameters. At the same time, the proposed hybrid model requires less data for training than a purely data-driven non-linear model or a hybrid model with a non-linear data-driven component. Less requirements on the training data than models with non-linear data-driven components, and a greater accuracy than a physical model with fitted but constant parameters, makes the presented approach attractive also in other subject domains.

1.1 Related Work

There is a rich literature on models for magnetostriction. Most of these models are inherently physics-based, building on existing models for the interplay between magnetization, stress, and magnetostrictive strain [2, 9, 10, 11, 20]. These models are usually evaluated

using finite elements methods and compared to experimental measurements. On the other end of the spectrum, a purely data-driven model has been proposed that estimates the harmonic components of magnetostrictive strain measurements from amplitudes and phases of magnetic flux by using a feed-forward neural network [19].

Hybrid models, i.e., models that combine physics-based with data-driven approaches, appear only sparsely in the literature. An early example is [11], which proposed a parameterized analytical model for magnetostrictive strain ε as a function of the magnetic field H [11, eq. (41)]. While this model is ad-hoc, it reproduces expected behavior if the parameters are fitted to experimental data. More recently, Zhu et al. proposed an extension of the two-dimensional magnetostriction model of [15] by letting model parameters vary with input data in a non-linear fashion [21]. These non-linear dependencies were obtained by fitting the resulting model to experimental data.

The approach proposed in this work differs from [11, 21]. Specifically, the first step of the proposed approach – fitting parameters to a physics-based model – resembles [11]; however, the proposed manuscript goes one step further in using these fitted parameters to obtain a linear data-driven model based on electrical measurements and coil dimensions. This is in contrast with [21], which employed a non-linear model with parameters estimated via "trial-and-error".

2 Dataset

2.1 Measurement System

Based on the patent [14], the CMS, shown in Figure 1, was built to determine the magnetic and magnetostrictive properties of a steel coil with a mass of up to 6,000 kg (the geometry of such a steel coil is shown in Figure 2). For that purpose, the steel coil is placed by crane on a coil lift truck which is moved with a semi-automatic control into the measurement cabin where the steel coil is energized. Therefore, in contrast to the standardized measurement methods, the Epstein and the single sheet tester [5], the CMS allows to measure the magnetostrictive properties of the entire coil without disassembly.

Generally, the mean specific losses and the magnetostrictive vibration of each steel coil are measured during a standardized measurement sequence covering flux densities from 1.0 T up to 1.9 T in steps of 0.05 T at 50 Hz and 60 Hz. The preparation of the specimen including the complete measurement sequence can be realized within 15 minutes. This allows a fast incoming goods inspection of each delivered steel coil. Within the CMS the magnetostrictive vibration of each steel coil is measured with acceleration transducers on the steel coils narrow side when it is energized (see Figures 1 & 2). A detailed description of the measurement system and first experimental results can be found in [16, 17].

2.2 Dataset Description

The analyzed dataset in this work contains measurement data on 3,665 coils of the same material for two suppliers, A and B. For supplier A data for 1,634 coils, for supplier B data for 2,031 coils is available. For each coil, several quantities are measured by the

Figure 1: Coil measurement system. The steel coil is placed by crane on a coil lift truck which is moved with a semi-automatic control into the measurement cabin where the steel coil is energized. Each steel coil is measured during a standardized measurement sequence covering flux densities from 1.0 T up to 1.9 T in 0.05 steps at 50 Hz and 60 Hz.

Figure 2: Geometry of a steel coil. D_i and D_a denote the inner and outer diameter of the coil, respectively.

Figure 3: Feature statistics. The figure compares S (3a–3c) and $\cos(\varphi)$ (3d–3f) for supplier A and B in relationships of measurement ID 1 (≈ 1.9 T), 7 (≈ 1.6 T) and 15 (≈ 1.0 T).

CMS, including the apparent power S in VA, the power factor $\cos(\varphi)$, the magnetic field H in A/m, the magnetic flux density B in T, and the effective vibration velocity v in $\mu\text{m/s}$. Each quantity is measured 15 times (ID = 1, ..., 15), where each measurement ID is defined by a target flux density (1.9 T for ID = 1, 1.6 T for ID = 7, 1 T for ID = 15, etc.). Each measurement is performed with a defined voltage, the measurement values for the magnetic flux density B are recorded. This work considers only measurements performed at a line frequency of 50 Hz. Figure 3 compares the data of both S and $\cos(\varphi)$ among suppliers A and B for three representative measurement IDs. In addition, each coil is described by its temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) before the measurement, its fill factor and its dimensions (see Figure 2), including inner and outer diameter in m, weight in kg, and width in m. Furthermore, the temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of both the measuring device and the current transformer are given, which accumulates to an 83-dimensional feature vector characterizing each coil.

2.3 Data Preprocessing

In the preprocessing part, coils showing anomalous observations were removed from the dataset to reduce bias in the model. Anomaly detection was done in a univariate setting by applying boxplot statistics to the effective vibration velocity v . Specifically, for every measurement ID, values outside of $[Q_1 - k \cdot \Delta Q; Q_3 + k \cdot \Delta Q]$ were flagged as anomalous observations, where Q_1 and Q_3 denote the lower and upper quartile, where $\Delta Q = Q_3 - Q_1$ denotes the interquartile range, and where k was chosen with $k = 3$. Then, each coil with at least one anomalous observation of v was removed entirely from the dataset. According to this procedure, 77 coils were marked as outliers, 28 for supplier A and 49 for supplier B, resulting in a dataset with a total number of 3,588 coils (1,606 coils for A and 1,982 coils for B, respectively).

3 Methodology

The proposed hybrid model consists of a physics-based non-linear part that estimates magnetostriction as a function of the magnetic field and that is parameterized by two coil-dependent parameters obtained via curve fitting. These parameters are estimated from coil measurements in a linear regression framework, constituting the data-driven part of the hybrid model. Model development and evaluation are described in detail below and summarized in Algorithm 1.

3.1 Physical Model for Magnetostriction

The magnetostrictive strain ε measures the mechanical deformation of steel due to magnetization M , taking external stress σ into account. Based on thermodynamical considerations, the strain ε of a material can be approximated by [8, eq. (7)]

$$\varepsilon \approx \frac{\sigma}{E} + \lambda_0(\sigma) + \frac{\lambda_s - \lambda_0(\sigma)}{M_{ws}^2} M^2 \quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modulus, λ_s is the maximum magnetostrictive strain, $\lambda_0(\sigma)$ describes the magnetoelastic coupling characteristics of the material, and M_{ws} is the magnetization when the domain wall shift reaches saturation. Strain is therefore influenced by external stress, magnetoelastic coupling, and magnetization. Approximating $\lambda_0(\sigma)$ and assuming no stress ($\sigma = 0$) leads to a simplified model for magnetostrictive strain as a function of magnetization [8, eq. (10)]:

$$\varepsilon \approx \frac{\lambda_s M^2}{M_{ws}^2} \quad (2)$$

The magnetization of the material is connected to the applied magnetic field H via the Jiles-Atherton model. At least in the non-saturated case, this model can be approximated by [8, eq. (2)]

$$M \approx \frac{\alpha_1}{\mu_0} \arctan \left(\frac{H}{\alpha_2} \right) \quad (3)$$

Data: $(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{H}_i)$ for all coils $i = 1, \dots$ from a given supplier and material
Dataset splitting: Split data in training X_t and evaluation set X_e . Define $I_t = \{i | \mathbf{x}_i \in X_t\}$ and $I_e = \{i | \mathbf{x}_i \in X_e\}$.
Non-linear least squares: Perform Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm to solve

$$(a_i, b_i) = \arg \min_{(a,b)} \sum_{j=1}^{15} \left(v_{i,j} - a \cdot \arctan(b \cdot H_{i,j})^2 \right)^2, \quad \forall i \in I_t$$

Linear regression: Compute the solution of the linear regression problems

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}_a &= (X_t^T X_t)^{-1} X_t^T \mathbf{a}_t \\ \hat{\beta}_b &= (X_t^T X_t)^{-1} X_t^T \mathbf{b}_t \end{aligned}$$

Estimation of effective vibration velocity using the estimated parameter $\hat{a}_i = \hat{\beta}_a^T \mathbf{x}_i$ and $\hat{b}_i = \hat{\beta}_b^T \mathbf{x}_i$:

$$\hat{v}_{i,j} = \hat{a}_i \cdot (\arctan(\hat{b}_i \cdot H_{i,j}))^2, \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, 15 \quad \text{and } i \in I_e$$

Calculation of the mean absolute error (MAE) for each ID:

$$\text{MAE}_j = \frac{1}{|I_e|} \sum_{i \in I_e} |v_{i,j} - \hat{v}_{i,j}|, \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, 15$$

Algorithm 1: Model Training and Evaluation.

where α_1 and α_2 are curve fitting parameters and μ_0 is the permeability of free space. Combining (2) with (3) yields

$$\varepsilon \approx a \cdot (\arctan(b \cdot H))^2 \quad (4)$$

where $b = 1/a_2$ and $a = \lambda_s a_1^2 / (M_{ws}^2 \mu_0^2)$.

3.2 Data-Driven Model for Physical Parameters (a, b)

It is assumed that a measurement dataset is available for training a data-driven model based on the physical model in (4). I_t denotes the set of indexes used for training, i.e., indexes of coil measurement data used in the training phase. As outlined in Section 2.2, for each coil, this dataset consists of coil temperature and coil dimensions, as well as of vectors containing measurements of the apparent power S , power factor $\cos(\varphi)$, magnetic flux B , magnetic field H , and effective vibration velocity v . Following the analysis in [17, Fig. 7 & 8], the effective vibration velocity is taken as a proxy for magnetostrictive strain ε . Specifically, let $v_{i,j}$ and $H_{i,j}$ denote the effective vibration velocity and magnetic field of coil i at measurement ID j , and let $\mathbf{v}_i = (v_{i,1}, \dots, v_{i,15})$ and $\mathbf{H}_i = (H_{i,1}, \dots, H_{i,15})$. Let furthermore \mathbf{x}_i denote a vector with 1 as the first element (for fitting an intercept)

Figure 4: Coil Measurements and Fitted Physical Model. The figure shows the effective vibration velocities for a selected coil, together with the physical model $a_i \cdot \arctan(b_i \cdot H)^2$ with coil-dependent parameters (a_i, b_i) , obtained via curve fitting using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm. The abscissa and ordinate display the magnetic field H and the effective vibration velocity v , respectively.

followed by all other measurements of coil i , including coil temperature and coil dimension. According to the dataset description in Section 2.2, this vector has length $p = 54$: From the 83 extracted features for each coil, 15 features are collected in the vectors \mathbf{v}_i and \mathbf{H}_i each, leaving 53 features and the entry 1 for \mathbf{x}_i . Let finally $X_t = (\mathbf{x}_i | i \in I_t)$ be a matrix where each row corresponds to the measurements of one coil, i.e., X_t is a $|I_t| \times p$ matrix.

Using the magnetic field and effective vibration velocity measurements, the coil-dependent parameters a_i and b_i in (4) (here extended with subscript i indicating the coil) are obtained by curve fitting by minimizing non-linear least squares through the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm [13]

$$(a_i, b_i) = \arg \min_{(a,b)} \sum_{j=1}^{15} \left(v_{i,j} - a \cdot \arctan(b \cdot H_{i,j})^2 \right)^2. \quad (5)$$

Figure 4 shows, for a selected coil i , the effective vibration velocities $v_{i,j}$, $j = 1, \dots, 15$, together with the function $a_i \cdot \arctan(b_i \cdot H)^2$, where (a_i, b_i) are obtained by curve fitting in (5). Based on the relatively small difference one can state that the physical model with fitted parameters explains the observed data well.

The physical parameters a_i and b_i , collected in vectors $\mathbf{a}_t = (a_i | i \in I_t)$ and $\mathbf{b}_t = (b_i | i \in I_t)$, are response variables for a regression problem. Specifically, linear regression

is performed to estimate the slope vectors β_a and β_b minimizing the sum of squared residuals, i.e.,

$$\hat{\beta}_a = \min_{\beta_a} \sum_{i \in I_t} (a_i - \beta_a^T \mathbf{x}_i)^2 = (X_t^T X_t)^{-1} X_t^T \mathbf{a}_t \quad (6a)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_b = \min_{\beta_b} \sum_{i \in I_t} (b_i - \beta_b^T \mathbf{x}_i)^2 = (X_t^T X_t)^{-1} X_t^T \mathbf{b}_t \quad (6b)$$

where $(\cdot)^T$ denotes matrix transposition.

3.3 Estimation of the Effective Vibration Velocity and Model Evaluation

Given the slope vectors $\hat{\beta}_a$ and $\hat{\beta}_b$ estimated from the training dataset I_t as described in Section 3.2, it is possible to estimate the effective vibration velocity via

$$\hat{v}_{i,j} = \hat{\beta}_a^T \mathbf{x}_i \cdot \arctan(\hat{\beta}_b^T \mathbf{x}_i \cdot H_{i,j})^2, \quad j = 1, \dots, 15 \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{H}_i are the measurement vector and vector of magnetic field measurements of coil i from the evaluation dataset I_e . To evaluate the quality of the overall hybrid model, the mean absolute error (MAE) is calculated on the evaluation set, i.e.,

$$\text{MAE}_j = \frac{1}{|I_e|} \sum_{i \in I_e} |v_{i,j} - \hat{v}_{i,j}|, \quad j = 1, \dots, 15. \quad (8)$$

4 Results

The data under investigation contains coils from two suppliers, A and B. For each of these coils, the parameters (a_i, b_i) from (4) are estimated using (5) and displayed in Figure 5. It can be seen that parameters of different coils differ in general, which is in line with the observation that each coil has its own characteristics and that the variability even within a given supplier can be non-negligible [17]. Moreover, one can see that the clouds of points for both suppliers differ in their means and variances.

Following this preliminary analysis, three models are compared in this section: The first model is the physical model (4) with the parameters (a_i, b_i) obtained from curve fitting described in (5) (TP-model). The second model is the proposed hybrid model and equivalent to the physical model (4) with parameters (\hat{a}_i, \hat{b}_i) , estimated as in Algorithm 1 (EP-model). Finally, the third model is equivalent to the physical model (4) with the parameters replaced by the mean of the parameters (MP-model) computed on the training set

$$\bar{a} = \frac{1}{|I_t|} \sum_{i \in I_t} a_i \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{b} = \frac{1}{|I_t|} \sum_{i \in I_t} b_i. \quad (9)$$

The TP- and MP-models are benchmarks to which the EP-model is compared. On the one hand, the error of the TP-model presents a lower bound for the error of the EP-model (under the assumption that the physical model (4) is unbiased). On the other

Figure 5: Coefficients (a_i, b_i) for the two suppliers.

hand, if the vector of coil measurements and coil dimensions is uncorrelated with the fitted parameters (a_i, b_i) , then it follows directly from the solution of the associated linear regression problems that $\hat{a}_i = \bar{a}$ and $\hat{b}_i = \bar{b}$, i.e., MP- and EP-model coincide. The MP-model therefore is expected to have an error at least as large as the EP-model.

For each supplier, 90% of the coils have been used for training ((5) and (9) for the MP- and (5) and (6) for the EP-model) and 10% for evaluation ((4) with the fitted, linearly estimated, or mean parameters for the TP-, EP-, and MP-model, respectively). In order to obtain reliable results, training and testing has been repeated 100 times using random splits of the coils. The results in Tables 1 and 2 display the mean MAE and its standard deviation (in brackets), organized by measurement ID, for all three models, for supplier A and B, respectively.

The results support the main point of the paper: The parameters (a_i, b_i) depend (linearly) on the coil measurements and coil dimensions. This can be concluded by observing that the mean MAE of the EP-model is generally lower than the mean MAE of the MP-model – taking coil measurements and coil dimensions into account improves estimation accuracy. For example, at ID = 1 (corresponding to a high flux density) in Table 2, the mean MAE is 30.48 for the EP-model and 41.85 for the MP-model; the difference is considerable in the light of the mean MAE of 10.19 for the TP-model. Furthermore, it can be seen that the EP- and MP-models have similar standard deviations for all IDs and both suppliers.

Although the EP-model performs considerably better than the MP-model for low IDs, it must be noted that for high IDs this advantage vanishes. Moreover, one can see that for these high IDs, which correspond to low values of the flux density, the MAEs approach

Table 1: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for supplier A organized per ID. The first column shows the result using the estimated parameters (\hat{a}, \hat{b}) . The second column consists of the MAE obtained taking the mean of the parameters (a, b) , i.e. constant within the supplier. The last column shows the result obtained using the parameters (a, b) , this is to be considered as a lower bound for the error using the hybrid-model (4). Brackets contain the standard deviation.

ID	EP-model (\hat{a}, \hat{b})	MP-model (\bar{a}, \bar{b})	TP-model (a, b)
1	48.39 (3.01)	56.43 (3.68)	16.97 (.81)
2	42.79 (3.23)	53.33 (3.68)	18.60 (.65)
3	39.87 (3.13)	48.51 (3.39)	20.52 (.64)
4	34.75 (2.77)	41.95 (3.19)	11.22 (.56)
5	31.74 (2.49)	38.36 (2.98)	5.93 (.39)
6	31.35 (2.35)	37.81 (2.77)	11.25 (.53)
7	31.35 (2.24)	37.87 (2.59)	16.47 (.55)
8	29.89 (2.09)	36.69 (2.50)	17.11 (.48)
9	26.07 (1.91)	33.99 (2.40)	13.38 (.39)
10	21.29 (1.71)	30.37 (2.37)	7.04 (.43)
11	18.31 (1.71)	27.61 (2.10)	7.85 (.53)
12	24.94 (1.45)	28.26 (1.31)	23.73 (.82)
13	27.08 (.96)	27.07 (.71)	27.16 (.64)
14	21.38 (.74)	21.05 (.56)	21.48 (.54)
15	15.46 (.58)	15.35 (.49)	15.55 (.46)

the MAE of the TP-model. More interestingly, the MAE for the TP-model increases for lower IDs despite decreasing effective vibration velocity. This is, most probably, an artifact of the fitting procedure (5), which inherently fits the parameters such that the curve well approximates ranges with large effective vibration velocities.

5 Discussion & Conclusion

In this study a new approach to model the magnetostriction in power transformers is presented. By leveraging the combined strengths of a data-driven approach and a physics-based model a hybrid model has been developed. Specifically, a linear model has been successfully used to estimate the parameters of the non-linear physics-based model from electrical coil measurements and coil dimensions. A separate set of experiments showed that replacing the linear regression model by a non-linear model did not improve performance. This was confirmed for both support vector regression under a cross-validation framework and for a neural network. Therefore, the combination of a non-linear physics-based and a linear data-driven model not only performs satisfactory in the present application, but also sits at a sweetspot regarding the trade-off between model accuracy and the amount of data required for training.

Based on the proposed hybrid model, values for new incoming coils can be predicted

Table 2: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for supplier B organized per ID. The first column shows the result using the estimated parameters (\hat{a}, \hat{b}) . The second column consists of the MAE obtained taking the mean of the parameters (a, b) , i.e. constant within the supplier. The last column shows the result obtained using the parameters (a, b) , this is to be considered as a lower bound for the error using the hybrid-model (4). Brackets contain the standard deviation.

ID	EP-model (\hat{a}, \hat{b})	MP-model (\bar{a}, \bar{b})	TP-model (a, b)
1	30.48 (1.81)	41.85 (2.27)	10.19 (.49)
2	26.95 (1.66)	42.48 (2.28)	5.11 (.36)
3	26.18 (1.62)	40.88 (2.09)	10.20 (.44)
4	23.86 (1.52)	36.92 (1.85)	9.37 (.41)
5	20.93 (1.38)	32.49 (1.69)	5.47 (.37)
6	18.93 (1.17)	29.26 (1.61)	4.78 (.31)
7	18.09 (1.07)	26.93 (1.47)	7.97 (.30)
8	17.41 (.86)	25.04 (1.40)	9.69 (.28)
9	15.39 (.84)	22.38 (1.28)	8.49 (.33)
10	12.74 (.72)	19.44 (1.18)	5.61 (.31)
11	10.71 (.64)	16.54 (.95)	4.68 (.27)
12	11.78 (.58)	14.24 (.56)	10.85 (.35)
13	13.39 (.52)	13.68 (.42)	13.37 (.37)
14	10.66 (.37)	10.84 (.34)	10.72 (.33)
15	7.41 (.30)	7.51 (.31)	7.40 (.30)

without the need to measure magnetostriction with vibration sensors. This enables companies to determine the magnetostrictive properties of new coils based on the history of measurements providing a parallel system that can serve as a control for the measurement system. Results show that the use of coil data is beneficial for the estimation and that the prediction is in agreement with the CMS. Furthermore, a comparison between predicted and measured magnetostriction could reveal areas of improvement in the predictive model as well as in the CMS.

Availability of data and materials

Data from Siemens AG Österreich for this study are not publicly available due to privacy considerations. Due to the data security of participants, data cannot be shared freely. Please directly refer to Siemens AG Österreich, the data provider for this study, to forward a request for data availability.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author's contributions

AC, GC, and BCG made substantial contributions to conception and design of the study and to the interpretation of the results. AC and GC performed the analysis. All authors have been involved in drafting and revising the manuscript.

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